

Energy recovery using piezoelectric cells: A comparison of compression and flexure

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Abstract— Piezoelectric materials are potentially useful for recovering vibrational energy from sources such as roads, vehicles, aircraft and human daily activity. This could lead to improved energy efficiency and autonomy of mobile systems. We compared compression and flexure as sources of energy recoverable by a piezoelectric cell, first using a dynamic model based on the modal spectral response. We then obtained stress-voltage curves using real loads in order to evaluate the power generated by the cell. Compression and flexure stresses were then compared in terms of measurable power. The model predicted the actual behavior of the piezoelectric cell at low vibrational frequencies. Considerably more energy would be recoverable from flexural loading than from compression loading. These findings should be taken into consideration when designing piezoelectric cells and positioning them for maximal energy recovery in motor vehicles or vibrating systems in general.

Index Term— Energy harvesting, Piezoelectric material, Dynamic modeling, Vibrations, Vehicle's energy efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

REDUCTION of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and replacement of fossil energy sources with carbon-neutral sources are the focus of the Paris agreement (COP 21) and recent legislation in many countries around the world. In Canada, transportation is the largest single emitter of greenhouse gases, contributing 27% of the total [1]. Of this portion, road vehicles account for 69%. Electrification of transportation is widely viewed as a way of reducing emissions. However, electric vehicles raise challenges, including energy

autonomy. Rechargeable batteries remain the only practical means of powering a personal motor vehicle. Much research is therefore underway to increase vehicle autonomy by optimizing energy use. So far, the best energy efficiency achieved by electric cars is about 50% [2]. In other words, about 50% of the battery energy is lost on a daily basis. Embedded sensors alone consume about 10% of the total energy used by a vehicle [3] and up to 14 % if the on-board computer is considered. Energy efficiency and energy recovery therefore represent huge opportunities for improving the acceptability of electric-powered vehicles. One promising approach appears to be energy harvesting. In addition to energy-saving algorithms, recycling energy losses back into the loop to power instrumentation could also improve vehicle energy efficiency.

Energy harvesting is becoming one of the most widely investigated ways of providing energy from sustainable sources [4], [5], [6], especially for wireless embedded smart sensors. The energy needs of such sensors in different situations has been evaluated [4] as have algorithms that address the mismatch between sensor demands and energy harvestable from plane aisle vibrations using piezoelectric devices [5]. This is of particular interest in rural communities and other off-grid situations [6]. Although computational approaches to optimization seem promising, they consume energy themselves. Using piezoelectric materials to harvest vibrational energy is a common approach [7], [8], [9] and the case of road and vehicles has been examined repeatedly [10], [11], [12], [13]. A test bench that reproduces road traffic piezoelectric effects has been developed [10], although the focus was exclusively on voltage whereas current seems crucial for evaluation of generated power. Important aspects of the

piezoelectric element such as technical specifications and the method of mounting in the test bench need to be clarified along with details regarding the mechanical amplifier. In laboratory loading tests for which piezoelectric element packaging is presented [11], no results of actual road tests are provided. One study does describe energy harvesting from road traffic with support by simulations [12]. The converters used to generate power are evaluated along with economic analysis of viability.

Modeling of piezoelectric energy harvesting has relied so far on constitutive equations [14], [15], differential equations [14], [16], [17], [18] or on finite-elements-based tools and simulations [19], [20], [15], [21]. No dynamic model has been presented in detail in any published article.

This article introduces a dynamic model for piezoelectric cells with experimental validation at low frequencies. The template of this model was derived from field data in the technical documentation provided with the piezoelectric cell. Energy harvesting under different forces at several frequencies was investigated with a two-fold aim: (i) To characterize the piezoelectric cell dynamic behavior at the selected frequencies and thereby validate the proposed model; (ii) To measure the energy generated using a real load and therefore provide a proof of concept or reveal ways to improve the energy harvesting process.

2. SYSTEM PRESENTATION

2.1. Energy harvesting using piezoelectric material

Piezoelectric materials have the property of transforming time-variable mechanical stress or strain into electrical energy and vice versa. They can be seen as electromechanical devices with mechanical and electrical behaviors included in the same element.

The electrical and mechanical behavior of piezoelectric elements has been modeled widely in the scientific and technical literature. Most models are based on differential equations or on constitutive equation 1.

$$\begin{pmatrix} T \\ D \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C^E & -e \\ e^S & \epsilon^S \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} S \\ E \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Which expresses the relationship between stress vectors S , strain T , electric field E and the electric displacement D .

The constitutive-equation-based model provides a general idea of the gain that determines the voltage and hence energy generated by the stress or strain applied to the piezoelectric element. However, the dynamic aspects of the element are not represented explicitly. A more detailed modal description of the piezoelectric element would be obtained from a comprehensive dynamic model.

2.2. Dynamic modeling

Summary analysis of the responses of piezoelectric elements usually reveals four spectral zones or modes: low frequency, mid frequency, resonance and high frequency. Fig. 1 shows a typical spectrum of this dynamic behavior.

Fig. 1. Typical spectral response of a piezoelectric element to input frequency

The modal response dynamics of a piezoelectric element gives an idea of the ratio between the voltage V and the input F (force, stress or strain).

In the low-frequency zone, the dynamics are consistent with a derivative component weighted by a gain K_d :

$$\frac{V}{F} = K_d s \quad (2)$$

Where s is the Laplace operator, which for pure harmonic signals becomes the Fourier variable $s = j2\pi f$, in which f is the frequency of the applied force, stress or strain and j is the pure imaginary number ($j^2 = -1$). The V/F ratio is thus proportional to frequency.

Throughout the mid-frequency zone, the gain stays constant as the applied force varies, indicating first-order dynamics with time constant τ compensating for the effect of the derivative component as follows:

$$\frac{V}{F} = \frac{K_d s}{1 + \tau s} \quad (3)$$

The third zone corresponds to resonance and represents a spectral response peak, indicating second-order differential dynamics, represented as follows.

$$\frac{V}{F} = \frac{K s}{(1 + \tau s)(s^2 + 2\xi\omega_0 s + \omega_0^2)} \quad (4)$$

In equation 4, gain K represents $K_d \omega_0^2$, the product of the derivative gain K_d and the square of the natural pulse ω_0 . This equation also contains damping coefficient ξ , which determines the value of the peak response.

The fourth zone features a sharp decrease of the ratio of measured output voltage to applied force as frequency

increases. This zone establishes an important indicator for validating the model represented in equation 4. In fact, the strongly negative slope suggests third-order dynamics. Moreover, the dynamic model resulting from this analysis finds support in many differential-equation-based models used in the literature. The following differential equation can be derived from function 4:

$$\frac{d^3V}{dt^3} + a_2 \frac{d^2V}{dt^2} + a_1 \frac{dV}{dt} + a_0V = b_0 \frac{dF}{dt} \quad (5)$$

3. TOOLS AND MATERIALS

3.1. Parameter identification protocol

The various parameters of the proposed model are identified and computed using experimental results.

The derivative gain parameter is determined in the first zone. At any frequency, the pulse and the corresponding ratio of the applied force to the generated voltage can be determined, and hence the derivative gain. For instance, at frequency $f = 1$ Hz, the ratio between the input and the output is 0.5 mV/G, where G stands for Gravity. The computed derivative gain K_d is then $0.5/2\pi f\omega_0^2$, that is, 0.08.

The parameters associated with first-order dynamics are determined using the second zone of the spectral response. The time constant τ is computed at the curve (around 7 Hz) where the gain is 70% (or -3 dB) of the flat region in this zone. The time constant τ can be calculated as the inverse of the pulse: $\tau = 1/2\pi f = 23$ ms.

In the third zone, the resonance pulse for high peaks can approximate the natural pulse. In fact, high peaks usually imply very small damping coefficients, typically about 0.1 or less. The natural pulse can then be computed using the resonance frequency f_r : $\omega_0 = 2\pi f_r = 125,600$ rad/sec. The third zone also allows computation of damping coefficient ξ . In fact, at the resonance frequency, the overshoot observed is 100 times higher than the gain in the flat portion of zone 2. The damping coefficient thus estimated is 0.07.

4. EXPERIMENTS

4.1. Test bench presentation

Flexure and compression tests on the piezoelectric cell were conducted at ambient temperature (25°C) using a servo-hydraulic fatigue machine (model MTS-370.10) equipped with a 100 kN load cell and hydraulic jaws.

Controlled displacement in sine wave form was applied with a constant displacement ratio R approaching zero. The displacement ratio is defined as the minimum displacement δ_{\min} divided by the maximum displacement δ_{\max} .

4.2. Experimentation protocol

For compression tests, the piezoelectric cell was glued between two rubber cushions using epoxy, as shown in Fig. 2. Four loads (50, 100, 150 and 200 N) were applied at four frequencies (1, 5, 7 and 10 Hz). The choice of frequencies was based on published spectral analyses suggesting that a typical vehicle experiences vibrational modes mainly in the 1–10 Hz range [22], [23].

Fig. 2. Configuration of the compression test apparatus

For flexure tests, the piezoelectric cell was installed in the middle of the lower surface of a beam as shown in Fig. 3. A deflection of 0.086 mm was applied at 1 Hz, 5 Hz, 7 Hz and 10 Hz and respective loads of 32 N, 35 N, 37 N and 40 N. Data were logged using an Arduino UNO R3 microcontroller board connected serially to a computer with PuTTY acquisition software. An output signal conditioning circuit was provided, since the piezoelectric cell output can reach 30 V at high loads, whereas the acquisition card input must be limited to 5 V. The voltage divider illustrated in Fig. 4 was used.

Fig. 3. Configuration of the flexure test apparatus

Fig. 4. Configuration of the data acquisition circuit

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Voltage/Force-Frequency curves for the compression and flexure tests

Fig. 5 shows the ratio of voltage generated by the force applied to the piezoelectric cell as a function of frequency in compression tests. The electrical power can be calculated by dividing the square of the voltage V by the load resistance 2R.

Fig. 5. Voltage/force versus frequency at 50 N (solid line), 100 N (long dash), 150 N (short dash) and 200 N (long and short dashes)

Fig. 6 shows the ratio obtained in flexure tests.

Fig. 6. Voltage/force versus frequency with an applied deflection of 0.086 mm.

5.2. Discussion

It is apparent in Fig. 5 that the voltage/force ratio increases with frequency at a constant rate until 5 Hz then at a slightly slower rate until 7 Hz and then slower again up to 10 Hz. This can be explained by the prevailing derivative dynamics at the lowest frequencies and at the onset of first-order dynamics. The trend was similar at all applied forces. This supports the hypothesis of proportionality between the applied force and the output voltage of the piezoelectric cell with some measurement and/or model error. However, the dynamic behavior shows that the voltage-force ratio depends somewhat on the frequency of the applied force and that second-order behavior will follow first-order behavior. Fig. 6 reveals that the piezoelectric cell is much more responsive to frequency in flexure tests than in compression tests. In the 1 Hz mode of loading, the gain is 2 mV/G compared to 0.5–0.8 mV/G for the compression test. The gains are respectively about 8 mV/G and 2 mV/G at 5 Hz, 10 mV/G and 2.5 mV/g at 7 Hz and 12 mV/G and 2.5–2.75 mV/G at 10 Hz. In this specific application, the voltage divider acts as the load, giving the generated power shown in TABLE I and II. It is clear that the power generated by compression at 50 N and 100 N is inferior to that generated by flexure at lower applied forces at all frequencies.

TABLE I
POWER (μ W) GENERATED BY THE PIEZOELECTRIC CELL AT

DIFFERENT FREQUENCIES AND APPLIED FORCES IN COMPRESSION TESTS

Force (N)	Frequency (Hz)			
	1	5	7	10
50	0.06	1.08	1.64	2.02
100	0.65	4.32	5.95	7.95
150	0.86	9.36	13.99	16.24
200	0.88	14.9	23.52	25.00

TABLE II
POWER (μ W) GENERATED AT DIFFERENT FREQUENCIES IN THE FLEXURE TEST WITH A DEFLECTION OF 0.086 MM

Frequency (Hz)	1	5	7	10
Force (N)	32	35	37	40
Power (μ W)	0.19	6.25	12	24

This result could justify orienting the future design of piezoelectric energy recovery systems in motor vehicles towards the capture of flexure strain. The results also provide support for the dynamic behavior of the proposed model and therefore support for a more precise representation of the dynamic behavior of the piezoelectric cell and hence a more powerful tool for predicting the power that could be recovered for energy harvesting.

6. CONCLUSION

We provide experimental results that characterize piezoelectric cell behavior for application to harvesting energy from vibrations in motor vehicles. A novel model is presented that describes the dynamic behavior of the cell at frequencies corresponding to dynamic modes of vehicle vibration. The experimental results validated the results of the proposed model at the frequencies of interest. Both compression and flexure tests were conducted. Flexure allowed recovery of considerably more power. This finding should be taken into consideration in the design of energy harvesting devices for vehicles. This difference in generated power suggests that locating piezoelectric cells where flexural force is maximal could increase energy recovery.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We thank the IRH and I2E3 laboratories as well as the Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières for supporting this work through a FIR grant, for the test materials and for tools that

allowed us to conduct and validate the experiments reported in this study.

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